

POZITSION MASALALARNING SHARTIGA ASOSAN TALABALARDA FAZOVIIY CHIZMALAR CHIZISH MALAKALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. *Muhandislik grafikasida ortogonal proeksiyalashdan tashqari yana narsalarni (buyumlar) uch o'lchamda (aksonometriyada) tasvirlash, texnik rasm va fazoviy chizma degan tushunchalar bor. Fazoviy chizma narsalarning fazodagi o'rini, bir biriga nisbatini va joylashuvini yaqqol tasvirlab beradi. Muallif ushbu maqolada pozitsion va metrik masalalar yechishda talabalarda fazoviy chizmalar hosil qilish malakalarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishni maqsad qilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar. *proeksiya, fazo, o'q chiziq, kesma, tekislik izlari, bissektisa, parallel, perpendikulyar, proeksiyalovchi yoki umumiy vaziyatdagi tekislik.*

Аннотация. *В инженерной графике, помимо ортогонального проецирования, существуют такие понятия, как изображение предметов в трех измерениях (в аксонометрии), технический рисунок и пространственный рисунок. Пространственная схема наглядно изображает положение предметов в пространстве, их соотношение и расположение. В данной статье автор стремится сформировать и развить у студентов навыки создания пространственных чертежей при решении позиционных и метрических задач.*

Ключевые слова: *Проекция, пространство, осевая линия, отрезок, следы плоскости, биссектриса, параллельная, перпендикулярная, проецирующая или плоскость общего положения.*

Abstract. *In engineering graphics, in addition to orthogonal projection, there are such concepts as depicting objects in three dimensions (in axonometry), technical drawing, and spatial drawing. A spatial diagram visually depicts the position of objects in space, their relationship, and arrangement. In this article, the author aims to form and develop students' skills in creating spatial drawings when solving positional and metric problems.*

Keywords: *Projection, space, axial line, segment, traces of a plane, bisector, parallel, perpendicular, projecting, or general-position plane.*

1-masala. Berilgan: Umumiy vaziyatda joylashgan AB ($A'B'$, $A''B''$) va EF ($E'F'$, $E''F''$) kesmalarining ortogonal proeksiyalari (1-rasm).

Aniqlash kerak: Asosi AB bo'lgan, C uchi EF kesmada yotuvchi, teng yonli uchburchak ABC ning ($AC=CB$) proeksiyalari topilsin. Bizga ma'lumki, asosi AB kesmani teng ikkiga bo'luvchi (K) va unga perpendikulyar bo'lgan Q (QAB) tekislikda yotuvchi barcha nuqtalar kesmaning A va B uchlaridan bir xil masofada bo'ladi (2-rasm). Demak:

1. K ($AK=KB$) nuqta orqali Q ($k'f'$, $k''f''$; $k'h'$, $k''h''$) tekislik o'tkaziladi. Teng yonli uchburchak yasash uchun Q tekislikda shunday nuqtani toppish kerakki, o'sha nuqta EF kesmaga tegishli bo'lsin.

2. EF kesmani Q tekislik bilan kesishuv nuqtasini topish kerak. Buning uchun EF kesma orqali yordamchi kesuvchi (T) tekislik o'tkaziladi.
3. T va Q ($T \cap Q$) tekisliklarning o'zaro kesishuv chizig'i MN ($M'N'$, $M''N''$) aniqlanib, MN chiziq bilan EF kesmaning kesishuv nuqtasi C (C' , C'') belgilanadi.
4. C (C' , C'') nuqta bilan AB kesmaning A va B uchlari tutashtirilib, asosi AB bo'lgan teng yonli ΔABC proeksiyalari topiladi.

1-rasm

2-rasm

2-masala. Berilgan: Umumiy vaziyatda ΔABC ($A'B'C'$, $A''B''C''$) tekislik va unda yotmagan D ($D'D''$) nuqta va MN ($M'N'$, $M''N''$) to'g'ri chiziq (3-rasm).

Topish kerak: D orqali MN chiziqni kesuvchi ΔABC tekislikka parallel to'g'ri chiziq o'tkazilsin.

Ma'lumki, ikki tekislik o'zaro parallel bo'lsa, birinchi tekislikda joylashgan har qanday chiziq, ikkinchi tekislikka parallel bo'ladi (4-rasm). Demak:

1. D nuqta orqali ΔABC tekislikda parallel bo'lgan DEF ($DE \parallel AB$; $DF \parallel AC$) tekislik o'tkaziladi. Bunda DEF tekislikda joylashgan barcha chiziqlar ABC tekislikka parallel bo'ladi.

2. MN to'g'ri chiziqni DEF tekislik bilan kesishuv nuqtasini topish uchun MN to'g'ri chiziq orqali P ($P \perp H$) tekislik o'tkaziladi.

3. P va DEF ($P \cap DEF$) tekisliklarning o'zaro kesishuv chizig'i 1,2 ($1'2'$, $1''2''$) aniqlanib, uning MN chiziq bilan kesishuv nuqtasi K ($K'K''$) belgilanadi.

4. DK ($D'K'$, $D''K''$) MN to'g'ri chiziqni kesuvchi va ΔABC tekislikka parallel kesmadir.

3-rasm

4-rasm

3-masala. Umumiy vaziyatda P tekislik izlari (P_v, P_H) va AB ($A'B', A''B''$) kesma berilgan (5-rasm).

Topish kerak: P tekislik izlaridan (P_v, P_H) bir xil uzoqlikdagi AB kesmada joylashgan nuqta K ($K'K''$) topilsin.

Ushbu masalada muallif fazoviy chizmani to'liq tahlil qilish orqali yechimini yaratib, ortogonal proyeksiyalarda bajarishni o'quvchiga havola qilishni lozim topdi. Demak:

1. P tekislikning izlarini (P_v, P_H) teng ikkiga ajratuvchi bissektisa proyeksiyalarini topish kerak.
2. Bissektisa orqali P tekislikka perpendikulyar bo'lgan Q ($Q \perp P$) tekislik o'tkazilishi lozim.
3. Q tekislik bilan AB ($AB \subset T$) to'g'ri chiziq kesmasini kesishuv chizig'i MN ($Q \cap T$) topiladi.
4. MN chiziq bilan AB kesmaning kesishuv nuqtasi K masalaning javobi bo'ladi.

Nuqta K - AB kesmadagi ($K \subset AB$) P tekislik izlaridan bir xil uzoqlikda joylashgan nuqtadir (6-rasm).

5-rasm

6-rasm

Ushbu fazoviy chizmalarni yaratish orqali (malakalarni shakllantirish) masalalarning qanday bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar, ularga yechim topish mumkin ekan. Shartlar turlicha bo'lgani bilan,

yechim yo‘li deyarli bir-biriga yaqindir. O‘quvchida grafik tasvirlash qobiliyatini shakllantirib, uning fazoviy tasavvurini o‘stiradi.

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